

Environmental Impact on Agriculture: WTO and Indian Economic Reforms

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Introduction:

It would rather foolish to hold too extreme views on environmental impact on Indian agriculture. For instance, the MET department pointed out that the global warming has nothing to do with the arrival and number of raining days in India in its recent forecast. Whereas it is commonly held view by the environmentalists that the USA and developed countries have been actively 12 percent of carbon dioxide composed to less emission on caused by developing countries. Therefore, it is necessary for developed countries rather than imposing some condition on developing countries in WTO agenda for negotiations. The degradation of forest, complex water pollution coupled with it unmindful use, use of chemical fertilizers in a disproportionate manner and the spraying of poisonous pesticides for weed control all have caused enough damage to Indian agriculture. In the eleventh plan the government is thinking of bringing about second green revolution with an objective of stepping up the growth rate in agriculture and bringing some second stage far reaching reforms so as to achieve a combined growth rate of above 10%. As a result of this, the environment has a serious impact on the agriculture sector in India in the multi-dimensional aspects. If the technology and extension services coupled with patenting of seeds by individuals or Multinational companies would cause a great degenerating impact on agricultural quantity and quality of production in India. As the nation is gripped with the idea of doubling the rate of growth of the agricultural output, the environment will be a direct victim if proper attention and steps are put in place. The purpose of the present is to give a description of the status of agricultural sector in India before the introduction of economic reforms. The achievements and the required second phase of reforms to bring about second green revolution and causes responsible for such an act is given a complementary treatment.

Part-I

The State of Art

Before any attempt is made, in understanding the requisites of launching pad for second green revolution duly supported by second stage of economic reform, save the impact of environment on Indian agriculture. It is imperative to know the state of art in Indian agriculture before the advent of economic reforms. However, the environment will receive its due share of treatment in following sections.

It is needless to recapitulate the fact that India truly heralded the green revolution way back in the year 1965. This revolution paved the way for food security needs and self sufficiency of the country in food and food matters. Indeed, it is noteworthy that the production of food during the period of green revolution increased to more than two hundred million tonnes which thereby could satisfy the hunger of the people (if managed well). Farther, there has been a substantial increase in the export of primary agricultural products which could bring foreign exchange improved the countries balance of trade.

The green revolution besides its impact on agricultural production had developed some of the cracks which started holding back the agricultural production. For this, not only there was a financial gap or credit gap for farmers but also the marketing of products had separate difficulties. The people, particularly experts started speaking in the tune that green revolution did not remain as green revolution. In fact some of the empirists went to the extent of

calling it a red revolution because of the uncontrolled problems beset with this revolution which started slowly bringing about the so called displacements in cultivation. The great tragedy of green revolution has been due to a host of mixed factors. For example,

1. Small landholders were unable to compete with the farmers of larger size. They were even made to sell their land make the way towards migration to urban areas.
2. The patented seeds by Multinational National Companies started rushing into the market and made the farmers a slave the improved seeds genes.
3. Similarly, the seeds could be used only once for all and the farmers inventories were of no use for re-sowing.
4. Besides, the seeds did not have full proof-ness. In the sense that the seed producing companies did not guarantee the quality of seeds. Many of the farmers had lot of difficulties and rope failures attributed to poor quality of seeds bought from MNCs.
5. The chemical fertilizers come to occupy a prominent place among the farmers who used the modern HYV seeds. Unfortunately some illiterate (or otherwise) farmers had a mind set that more fertilizer would result in increase in more yield.
6. The use of more water (with a large quantity waste method) comes to occupy the minds of farmers in their greed for increase in production.

An examination of state of art of Indian agriculture also indicates the fact that the production, storage and marketing too had a set of difficulties which were beyond their grasp and reach. The storage facilities were very poor. The bulk of the purchase was done by the government (to be provided to public distribution system). They did not have comparative prices in the market. Over and above, they depended on support price from the government. The support price too was not remunerative or profitable for the farmers. The period under consideration exhibits the excessive use of pesticides for controlling new grown weeds and unseen crop diseases.

Part II

Second generation Reforms

There are a number of reform steps which have been spelled out recently by the government these are as follows:

1. The banks should provide greater quantum of credit at a reduced rate of interest, that is, to say about 7% per annum. This is the basic responsibility of the nationalized commercial banks and the Grameena Banks without exception to the co-operative banks. The government feels that the co-operative banks have larger network and has large number of members. Therefore, channalising credit through these basic institutions would ensure credit needs of the farmers.
2. The government is also aware of the subsidies of Rs.24.000 crores given to fertilizers companies. However, the philosophy of the government is that the fertilizer companies should become competitive and can sell their output in the free market. Whereas, the government should provide direct subsidy to the farmers. This method would help the farmers directly and would result in cost effectiveness with the use of fertilizer.

3. The third proposal as a component of second generation reform so as to bring about second green revolution in the Indian farm sector contemplated by the government is that the genetic seeds research which has been undertaken by governmental agricultural research institutes and laboratories and their results be made available to the farmers.
4. The reform step also included growth emphasis on extension services in the wake of new genetic seeds, application of fertilizer, breeding of new seeds etc.
5. The second generation reform has placed greater emphasis on organic farming and economical use of water and changes in the method of cultivation, including that of cropping pattern.

Part-III

Environmental Problems

There are directly man made and indirectly man made together, the natural factors which have degraded the environment insofar as the agriculture sector in India is concerned. The craze for producing more and more, routine cropping pattern, method of cultivation has degraded the various components of environment. Undoubtedly, the agriculture in the past was considered as a way of life. But today the agriculture has become a threat to the life and its existence, not only to the but also to a large number of animals, plants and other species of birds, the problem has become so serious that unless the immediate steps are taken the environment will effect the agriculture sector to the extent that it would result in an increase in the portion of barren land by more than 25%. It may be recalled that David Ricardo who was the first to give greater attention to the land was clever enough to classify lands into various categories. The impact on environment on Indian agriculture can be understood from the following tabular note,

The Causalities

SL .No	The Causes	Type of Impact	Remarks
1	Traditional method of cultivation	Greater pleasure only on the upper crust soil of about 6-8"	Loss of fertility and require more man days and use of bullocks. Gross and other weeds get greater shelter.
2.	The use of Tractor	Unmindful penetration into the deep soil and rain water drain will result in loss of fertility.	This is very serious when cultivable land is naturally sloppy and is not created by hard bonds.
3	Repeated cropping pattern (greed to take advantage of market price)	Degradation of soil quality and fertility	Decline in field may become barren.
4	More and more use of chemicals fertilizers	Salinity in land resulting decline in productivity	Disproportionate use by unmindful farmers has reduced the yield and made the land uncultivable. The output contains more portions of fertilizers and unfit for consumption.

5	The greater use of pesticides	Kills the beneficial genes available in the land	Get mixed up with air and absolute in rain waters percolate into the underground water.
6	Use of more and more water	The runoff of fertile elements, damage to crop yield	An unscientific use of quantity of water results in waste of scarce natural resources.
7	Intensive and extensive irrigation	Results in unscientific use of water	Reduction in ground water table
8	The system of Harvesting (convention or mechanical)	Generation of large quantity of agricultural wastages (some time used as fodder)	No proper method by farmers to use the agricultural wastage for making green components
9	After harvest using the land for grazing	Results loss of fertility	The grazing by goats etc has been considered as more seriously damaging factor for fertility.

The farmers grows same crop from year to year without the botheration for productivity yield. They are influenced by the market price of their products. Therefore it is well fact that repeated cultivation of the same crop will reduce certain proteins of the soil and even go to the extent of extension of pretense in the long run resulting in a sustainable reduction in output.

Part- IV

Remedial Measures: An Evaluation

The important measures to be followed in this context have been listed in the following.

1. The new and scientific cultivation of land by making use of sound techniques and machinery. This would ensure no soil erosion and help in protecting the fertility content in the soil.
2. The use of conventional fertilizer at an appropriate time with a strategy for sound mixing with the soil is considered as an important step which would ensure a long term sustainable fertility in the soil. The Cowden would also bring about greater strength in the soil quality which can withstand the environmentally influencing diseases to the crops.
3. The farmers should be trained to undertake the cultivation of rare medicinal plants. In fact a country in the Asian subcontinent, India has large number of medicinal plants which have not been undertaken for commercial production and export.
4. The Indian species and coffee have a distinct flavor and have substantial international demand what we need is to enhance the cultivation of these products and can earn substantial amount of foreign exchange.
5. It has come to the attention of automobile engineers that there are some agricultural products which are used as effective bio-diseases. Bio-diseases could find a great place in the Indian Economy.

Conclusion

India has very ambiguous problems of economic development during the eleventh and twelfth plans. It want to achieve a double digit rate of growth a greater emphasis on traditional sector i.e. agriculture. The green revolution and first generation reforms in this sector have produced a mixed result in which plenty and poverty have to coexist. Therefore great thrust is placed on 2nd green revolution second generation reforms to keep the agricultural sector greening. The alternative method of land use cultivation, cropping pattern, water use and use of natural fertilizers more than chemical fertilizers have been found to be in the place.

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